

Growth and Characterization of Glycine Oxalate Crystal

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Abstract

Glycine Oxalate (abbreviated as GO), $C_2H_6NO_2.C_2HO_4$, single crystal was grown by the solution growth technique. The as-grown colourless GO crystal was characterized by XRD and FTIR spectroscopic methods to study the structural and vibrational characteristics of the crystal. XRD pattern indicates that the crystal belongs to the monoclinic structure. FTIR spectrum shows that the vibrational characteristics of organic molecules of the crystal. Optical characteristics of the crystal were studied by UV-VIS-NIR (Ultraviolet - Visible - Near Infrared) spectroscopy. Optical transmittance and energy band gap (E_g) of the crystal were determined from $T\% - \lambda$ and $(\alpha h\nu)^2 - h\nu$ relationship.

Keywords: Glycine Oxalate, $C_2H_6NO_2.C_2HO_4$, solution growth technique, XRD, FTIR, monoclinic, UV-VIS-NIR

Introduction

New non-linear optical (NNLO) frequency conversion materials can have a significant impact on laser technology, optical communication and optical data storage technology. Materials with nonlinear electro optic properties have a role in modern optoelectronics that is analogous to that of non-linear electronic circuit elements in conventional electronics [Becker, 1998]. Organic materials have been of particular interest because the non linear optical responses in this broad class of materials is microscopic in origin, offering an opportunity to use theoretical modeling coupled with synthetic flexibility to design and produce novel materials. Further investigations on organic NLO materials have subsequently produced very good materials with highly attractive characteristics [Al-Hawery, 1998].

Many researchers have investigated the properties of pure glycine and its derivatives [Arivuoli, 2001]. Glycine oxalate is another nonlinear optical crystal, in the family of glycine derivative. The single crystal analysis was performed and the glycine molecule exists in the cationic form with a positively charged amino group and an uncharged carboxylic acid group, while the oxalic acid molecule exists in a mono-ionized state in the crystals. The hydrogen bonds that stabilize the molecules are interconnected between the amino and carboxyl groups of adjacent molecules. Materials with nonlinear electro-optic properties have a role in modern optoelectronics, hence, Glycine Oxalate single crystal was selected and characterized by XRD, FTIR and UV-VIS-NIR spectroscopy for the applications of optical materials.

Crystal Growth and Measurements

Glycine Oxalate (GO), $C_2H_6NO_2.C_2HO_4$ have been grown by solution growth technique. Analar (AR) grade Glycine ($C_2H_5NO_2$) and Oxalic acid ($H_2C_2O_4$) salt powders with equimolar ratio were used as the starting materials to grow the GO crystal. The distilled-water was used as the solvent to prepare saturated solution.

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The solution was slowly evaporated at temperature higher than the room temperature (typically 40°C to 45°C) to dissolve all of the salts in the solvent. The solution was filtered into the beaker and covered with thin plastic. Then the beaker placed at room temperature (29°C) for three days. Transparent and colourless seed crystals were drawn in solution. The seed crystals were collected with tweezers and placed on filtered paper to dry at room temperature. After three weeks, the enough size crystals were selected for the XRD and FTIR spectroscopic measurements. Photograph of the GO crystals are shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Photograph of the Glycine Oxalate

A powder X-ray diffractometer (RIGAKU MULTIFLEX) that was equipped with a CuK_α – radiation source used for the structural analysis of the sample. The main reflections in the range of $10^\circ < 2\theta < 70^\circ$ were observed and the collected data were used to investigate the unit cell parameters from the observed 2θ values with JCPDS (Joint Committee on Powder Diffraction Standards). FTIR transmission spectrum of Glycine Oxalate (GO), $\text{C}_2\text{H}_6\text{NO}_2 \cdot \text{C}_2\text{HO}_4$ crystal was observed by PC-controlled SHIMADZU FTIR-8400 spectrophotometer. UV-VIS-NIR transmission spectrum was observed by PC-controlled SHIMADZU UV-1800 Spectrophotometer in the wavelength range of 190 nm – 1100 nm.

Results and Discussion

XRD Study

Powder XRD pattern of Glycine Oxalate (GO) crystal is shown in Figure 2. The observed diffraction peaks and corresponding the diffraction angles “ 2θ ”, atomic spacing “ d ”, Miller indices (hkl) and peak height of the crystal were compared with Joint Committee on Powder Diffraction Standard (JCPDS) data library files of (i) Cat. No. 30-0624 > $\text{C}_2\text{H}_2\text{O}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ – Hydrogen Oxalate Hydrate and (ii) Cat. No. 06-0230 > $\text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{NO}_2$ – Glycine.

As shown in XRD pattern, the observed XRD lines were identified by JCPDS file. The line at the diffraction angle of 30.200° or ($\bar{1}11$) plane is the strongest in intensity ($I=100\%$) and it dominated on others planes (peaks). XRD pattern shows that Glycine Oxalate (GO) crystal analogous to monoclinic structure at room temperature. The lattice parameters are

evaluated by using the equation of $\frac{1}{d^2} = \frac{1}{\sin^2 \beta} \left(\frac{h^2}{a^2} + \frac{k^2 \sin^2 \beta}{b^2} + \frac{l^2}{c^2} - \frac{2hlc \cos \beta}{ac} \right) = \frac{4 \sin^2 \theta}{\lambda^2}$, where “ θ ” is the

diffraction angle ($^\circ$), “ d ” is the atomic spacing (\AA), (hkl) is the Miller indices, “ λ ” is the wavelength of incident X-ray and “ a, b, c ” are the lattice parameters (\AA) of a unit cell. In the

present work, the lattice parameters of the crystal are obtained as $a = 11.25 \text{ \AA}$, $b = 3.39 \text{ \AA}$, $c = 6.11 \text{ \AA}$ and $\beta = 92.57^\circ$ respectively.

FTIR Spectroscopic Study

FTIR transmission spectrum of GO crystal is shown in Figure 3. Glycine Oxalate (GO), $\text{C}_2\text{H}_6\text{NO}_2 \cdot \text{C}_2\text{HO}_4$ crystal, of course, is an organic compound. According to vibrational theory, wavenumbers of organic compounds are generally appeared in the regions of over the wavenumber 1500 cm^{-1} . These are often shifted into the low and high frequency regions.

Figure 2. XRD pattern of Glycine Oxalate (GO) crystal

Figure 3. FTIR transmission spectrum of Glycine Oxalate (GO) crystal

In the present work, the absorption lines at over the frequency 1400 cm^{-1} indicated that the organic molecules in GO crystal.

In this FTIR spectrum, ten absorption lines appeared in the wavenumbers range of $400 \text{ cm}^{-1} - 4000 \text{ cm}^{-1}$. The detail assignments of observed wavenumbers (absorption lines) and corresponding vibrational characteristics and mode assignments of constituent molecules in the crystal are assigned with standard data and tabulated in Table 1.

Table 1. Wavenumbers and corresponding vibrational mode assignments of Glycine Oxalate (GO) crystal

Wavenumber (cm^{-1})	Vibrational Characteristics	Molecule
480	Stretching	NH_3^+
515	Rocking	COO
581	Wagging	COO
708	Bending	COO
868, 901	Stretching	C—C
970	Rocking	NH_3^+
1017	Stretching	O—H—O
1098	Rocking	NH_3^+
1119, 1231	Bending	O—H—O
1323	Wagging	CH_2
1427	Scissoring	CH_2
1503, 1587	Asymmetric deformation	NH_3^+
1721	Stretching	C = C
1921, 2554, 2693	Combination	NH_3^+ & O—H—O
2874	Symmetric stretching	CH_2
3227	Asymmetric stretching	NH_3^+
3406	Symmetric stretching	O—H—O
3447	Asymmetric stretching	O—H—O

UV-VIS-NIR Spectroscopic Study

Ultraviolet-Visible-Near infrared (UV-VIS-NIR) spectroscopy involves the absorption of Ultraviolet-Visible-Near infrared light by a molecule causing the promotion of an electron from a ground electronic state to an excited electronic state. The UV-VIS-NIR optical transmission spectrum of the Glycine Oxalate (GO), $\text{C}_2\text{H}_6\text{NO}_2 \cdot \text{C}_2\text{HO}_4$ crystal was collected in UV-VIS-NIR region (190 nm – 1100 nm) by using UV-1800 UV-VIS-NIR Spectrophotometer is shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4. UV-VIS-NIR spectrum of Glycine Oxalate (GO) crystal

In the spectrum, the sample demonstrates that highest transmittance of throughout the Ultraviolet-Visible-Near infrared (UV-VIS-NIR) region, i.e., in the wavelength range of 315

nm – 1100 nm. In the wavelength range of 230 nm – 315 nm, the transmission of the UV and VIS light rapid increased in the sample and in the wavelength range of 315 nm – 1100 nm, the transmission of the high UV, VIS and NIR light nearly constant. It can be said that the sample exhibited as the optical transparent material in the wavelength range of 315 nm – 1100 nm.

The theory of optical transmission gives the relationship between the absorption coefficient α and the photon energy has a relation; $\alpha = -\ln(1/T)$. Figure 5 shows the plot of the variation of $(\alpha hv)^2$ with the photon energy hv of the GO crystal. The average band gap of the GO was determined from the interception of linear portion of the $(\alpha hv)^2$ vs. hv plots on the hv axis and obtained as 1.21 eV.

Conclusion

Glycine Oxalate (GO), $C_2H_6NO_2 \cdot C_2HO_4$ crystal was grown by solution growth technique. XRD pattern indicates that the GO crystal belongs to monoclinic structure and the lattice parameters of the crystal are $a = 11.25 \text{ \AA}$, $b = 3.39 \text{ \AA}$, $c = 6.11 \text{ \AA}$ and $\beta = 92.57^\circ$ respectively. Twenty- one absorption lines are found in the FTIR spectrum.

Fig 5 Plot of the $(\alpha hv)^2$ vs hv graph of Glycine Oxalate (GO) crystal

These lines are characteristics of organic molecules that constituent in the GO crystal. From the collected UV-VIS-NIR transmission spectrum, in the wavelength range 230 nm – 315 nm, the transmission of the UV and VIS light rapid increased in the sample and in the wavelength range 315 nm – 1100 nm, the transmission of the high UV, VIS and NIR light nearly constant. It shows that the GO crystal is an optical transparent material in the wavelength range 315 nm – 1100 nm. Experimental results indicated that the GO crystal can be utilized for UV-VIS-NIR optical windows material. Furthermore, the GO crystal can be used for SHG from a laser operating at 1064 nm (IR region) or other optical applications in the green, yellow and red region.

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